

1 **Exploring tropical freshwater soundscapes in Southeast Asia: insights into**
2 **auditory sensory adaptation of wild Siamese fighting fish *Betta splendens***

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19 Abstract

20 While soundscapes shape the structure and function of auditory systems over evolutionary
21 timescales, there is limited information regarding the adaptation of wild fish populations to their
22 natural acoustic environments. This is particularly relevant for freshwater ecosystems, which are
23 extremely diverse and face escalating pressures from human activities and associated noise
24 pollution. The Siamese fighting fish *Betta splendens* is one of the most important cultured species
25 in the global ornamental fish market and is increasingly recognized as a model organism for
26 genetics and behavioural studies. This air-breathing species (Anabantoidei), characterized by the
27 presence of a suprabranchial labyrinth organ, is native to Southeast Asia and inhabits low flow
28 freshwater ecosystems that are increasingly threatened due to habitat destruction and pollution.

29 We characterized the underwater soundscape, along with various ecological parameters, across
30 five marshland habitats of *B. splendens*, from lentic waterbodies to small canals near a lake in
31 Chiang Rai province (Thailand). All habitats exhibited common traits of low dissolved oxygen
32 and dense herbaceous vegetation. Soundscapes were relatively quiet with Sound Pressure Level
33 (SPL) around 102-105 dB re 1 μ Pa and most spectral energy below 1000 Hz. Sound recordings
34 captured diverse biological sounds, including potential fish vocalizations, but primarily insect
35 sounds. Based on Auditory Evoked Potential (AEP) recordings, we identified sex-specific
36 differences and a best hearing range within 100-400 Hz. This low-frequency tuning highlights the
37 potential susceptibility of *B. splendens* to anthropogenic noise activities.

38 This study provides first characterization of the auditory sensitivity and natural soundscape of *B.*
39 *splendens*, establishing an important ground for future hearing research in this species. The
40 information provided on the auditory sensory adaptation of *B. splendens* emphasizes the
41 importance of preserving quiet soundscapes from lentic freshwater ecosystems.

42

43 **Keywords:** Siamese fighting fish, ambient noise, freshwater acoustics, hearing thresholds,

44 auditory evoked potentials

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46 **Introduction**

47 Although freshwater ecosystems occupy a small portion of the Earth's surface (0.8%) and
48 just 0.01% of the total water on Earth, these habitats are home to over 12,000 fish species and
49 nearly 43% of all modern fish (Dudgeon et al., 2006; Nakatani et al., 2011). Freshwater fishes are
50 also known to play a key role in controlling the trophic structure of their ecosystems (Villéger et
51 al., 2017; Su et al., 2021). While this remarkable biodiversity has been continuously documented,
52 the diversification of freshwater fishes on a global scale and the environmental pressures driving
53 their speciation remain largely unexplored (Manel et al., 2020; Cerezer et al., 2023).

54 Freshwater habitats have traditionally been characterized in terms of physical, chemical,
55 and ecological parameters (Thomson et al., 2001; Belmar et al., 2019; Picado et al., 2020) but very
56 limited information exists on their acoustic features (Tonolla et al., 2010; Desjonquères et al.,
57 2015; Lara & Vasconcelos 2019; Rountree et al., 2020; Decker et al., 2020). While several studies
58 focused on the biological sounds produced by soniferous fish species (Anderson et al., 2008;
59 Montie, et al., 2015), some researchers described other biophonies such as insect sounds
60 (Desjonquères et al., 2020) and acoustic patterns associated to geophysical processes such as
61 hydraulic turbulence or sediment transport (Tonolla et al., 2011).

62 Underwater soundscapes can exhibit remarkable complexity, often surpassing terrestrial
63 acoustic environments in richness of information (Fay, 2009). This understanding has become
64 increasingly evident as fish species demonstrate the capability to detect and process both sound

65 pressure and particle motion, as well as to perform auditory scene analysis and sound source
66 localization (Hawkins & Popper, 2018; Popper & Hawkins, 2019, 2021; Veith et al., 2024). The
67 limitations of other sensory channels such as vision, olfaction, and touch in the aquatic
68 environment, particularly in providing rapid, long-distance, and tridimensional information, make
69 sound an exceptionally efficient information carrier for most aquatic organisms (Popper &
70 Hawkins, 2019, 2021).

71 By listening to the aquatic environment, fish can extract key biotic cues concerning the
72 presence of conspecifics and heterospecifics, including potential mates, prey, and predators
73 (Putland et al., 2019). Additionally, they may detect abiotic information for orientation, such as
74 sounds from wind, water currents, turbulence, and moving substrate (e.g., Lagardere et al., 1994).

75 Many fish species that live in freshwater environments exhibit higher auditory sensitivity
76 and/or an extended frequency bandwidth, due to accessory structures that enhance hearing by
77 acoustically coupling air-filled cavities to the inner ear (Ladich, 2000). Examples of such
78 structures are the Weberian apparatus found in Ostariophysi, or adaptations like the air-breathing
79 organ in Anabantoidei, which allows them to survive in low-oxygen stagnant waters (Yan, 1998;
80 Ladich & Yan, 1998; Ladich & Popper, 2004). The sensory adaptation of these fishes to their
81 highly diverse acoustic habitats, particularly their ability to extract relevant biological
82 information, remains poorly investigated. Few studies suggested that acoustic communication
83 was not the primary selective pressure involved in the evolution of their auditory abilities
84 (Ladich, 2000), emphasizing that the detection of acoustic cues from sources other than
85 conspecifics might have been crucial. This lack of information calls for further research on
86 otophysan species, which mostly inhabit freshwater ecosystems increasingly threatened by
87 habitat destruction and pollution (Golzan et al., 2019; Rountree et al., 2020).

88 The Siamese fighting fish *Betta splendens* (Anabantoidei: Osphronemidae) is one of the
89 most important cultured species in the global ornamental fish market, having undergone extensive
90 selective breeding for distinctive physical traits and behaviors (Simpson, 1968; Kwon et al., 2022).
91 Wild-type populations of this species persist in regions of Southeast Asia, including Thailand, the
92 northern Malay Peninsula, Cambodia, Indonesia and southern Vietnam, where they inhabit poorly
93 oxygenated freshwater environments such as small ponds and rice paddies (Hui & Nga,
94 2005; Kowasupat et al., 2012; Panijpan et al., 2017). As an anabantoid fish, *B. splendens* has
95 developed a highly folded and vascularized accessory breathing organ from the epibranchial bone,
96 termed the labyrinth organ (Adamek-Urbańska et al., 2021). This apparatus allows extracting
97 oxygen from air, equipping anabantoids to persist in hypoxic and polluted water (Tate et al., 2017).

98 Several studies on Siamese fighting fish, using both wild and domesticated strains, have
99 shown the potential of using this species for ecotoxicology (Tudor et al., 2019) and for decoding
100 the genomic and physiological mechanisms of behavior, particularly aggression (Fan et al.,
101 2018; Ramos & Gonçalves, 2019; Kwon et al., 2022; Ramos & Gonçalves, 2022; Palmiotti et al.,
102 2023). However, there are very few studies focusing on the species' natural habitat and no
103 information exists on its natural soundscape and auditory sensitivity.

104 In this study, we characterized the underwater soundscape and various ecological
105 parameters across different marshland habitats of *B. splendens*, ranging from lentic waterbodies to
106 small canals, in Chiang Rai province, northern Thailand. Additionally, we assessed the auditory
107 sensitivity of a wild strain originated from the same region, including males and females, to
108 evaluate the species' sensory adaptation to its natural acoustic environment and compare it with
109 other sympatric species.

110

111 **Methods**

112 **Test animals**

113 The Siamese fighting fish (*B. splendens*) used for audiometry purposes were 8 months old,
114 consisting of 5 males (31.98 ± 5.9 mm standard length, mean \pm standard deviation) and 6 females
115 (29.65 ± 3.97 mm). These fish belonged to the 10th generation, originating from adult fish initially
116 provided by suppliers in Chiang Rai, Thailand. They were bred and reared at the fish facility of
117 the University of Saint Joseph (Macao), following previously described procedures (Ramos &
118 Gonçalves, 2019, 2022). The fish tanks were maintained at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and under 12:12 light-dark
119 photoperiod. All animals were fed twice daily with a mixture of dry food (pellets from various
120 brands) and live artemia. Fish health status was monitored daily based on their feeding activity,
121 swimming behaviour, and the absence of apparent diseases.

122 Test subjects were initially maintained in mixed-sex stock tanks (50 cm width x 30 cm
123 length x 25 cm height) equipped with external filtering system and enriched with aquatic
124 vegetation and small ceramic shelters. Each tank housed a maximum of 50 fish, and presented a
125 background Sound Pressure Level (SPL) of 130-136 dB re 1 μPa (based on LZS, i.e. RMS sound
126 level obtained with slow time and linear frequency weightings; flat weighting: 6.3 Hz and 20 kHz;
127 see below measuring equipment). Prior to audiometry, fish were isolated in small individual tanks
128 (28 cm width x 14 cm length x 20 cm height; 4.5 L) for one week under lab silent conditions with
129 SPL varying between 103 and 108 dB re 1 μPa . Both male and female specimens were tested in
130 both the morning and afternoon periods, on alternating days. After the audiometry tests, the
131 animals recovered in isolated tanks with aerated system water and were later returned to the fish
132 facility. These fish remained in isolated tanks and were only used in further experiments at least 1
133 month later.

134 All experimental procedures complied with the ethical guidelines enforced at the
135 University of Saint Joseph and approved by the Division of Animal Control and Inspection of the
136 Civic and Municipal Affairs Bureau of Macao, license AL017/DICV/SIS/2016.

137

138 **Field sound recordings**

139 Field recordings were conducted in various locations within marshland habitats in Chiang
140 Rai (Northern Thailand), where the study species had been observed in previous studies (Ramos
141 & Gonçalves, 2019, 2022). These marshlands were modified for agricultural purposes, featuring
142 stagnate pools, lentic canals, and drainage dikes to manage the water supply. Ambient sound
143 recordings and Sound Pressure Level (SPL) measurements were carried in five distinct locations
144 near the Chiang Saen Lake, Chiang Saen District (CS) and the Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST),
145 Wiang Chai District (Fig. 1 Table 2): CS1 – drainage canal bordered by tall dense vegetation; CS2
146 - water body within an extensive mudflat with short herbaceous vegetation; RST1 – canal
147 surrounded by dense vegetation with presence of water buffalos; RST2 and RST3 – water bodies
148 in marshland with diverse herbaceous plants, including grasses, sedges, rushes, and other aquatic
149 plants. Overall, these freshwater habitats exhibited variable turbidity, brownish-coloured water
150 and muddy clay substrate, similarly to previously described habitats for the study species (Nur et
151 al., 2022).

152 An initial assessment of the water physico-chemical properties was carried out using a
153 handheld multi parameter sensor (Pro Plus, YSI, USA) for each of the study locations. The sound
154 recording protocol followed previous procedures by Lara & Vasconcelos (2019). The ambient
155 noise and SPL were recorded using a hydrophone (Brüel & Kjær 8104, Naerum, Denmark;
156 frequency range: 0.1 Hz–120 kHz, sensitivity of – 205 dB re 1 V/ μ Pa) connected to a hand-held

157 sound level meter with sound recording function (Brüel & Kjær 2250). The hydrophone was
158 attached to a pole and positioned in the middle of the water column avoiding direct contact with
159 substrate and vegetation.

160 Sound recordings, with a sampling frequency of 48 kHz, consisted of two consecutive 15
161 min sessions per site. The equivalent continuous SPL (L_{Zeq} ; flat weighting: 6.3–20 kHz) averaged
162 over 60 s was obtained six times per site - three times immediately before and after the overall 30
163 min recording. L_{Zeq} (also known as L_{Leq}) is a measure of averaged energy in a varying sound field
164 and is commonly used in environmental noise studies (ISO 1996 2003). The field work was
165 conducted in May 2024 under tropical dry season conditions in the absence of rain. All sound
166 recordings were performed away from human populations, hence no ethical concerns related to
167 accidentally recording human activity were present.

168

169 **Sound analysis**

170 Sound recordings were initially analyzed using Raven 1.5 (Bioacoustic Research Program,
171 Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology, NY, USA). Both aural and visual inspection of all sound
172 recordings were applied to identify potential sound sources.

173 Spectral analysis was performed using Adobe Audition 3.0 (Adobe Systems Inc., San José,
174 CA, USA) based on the overall 30 min per site. The Power Spectral Density (PSD) level, expressed
175 in dB re 1 $\mu\text{Pa}^2/\text{Hz}$, as well as the absolute sound spectra level in dB re 1 μPa , were determined by
176 using the averaged L_{Zeq} values calculated for each site, in accordance with the methods outlined
177 in prior research (Amoser & Ladich, 2010; Lara & Vasconcelos, 2019). The PSD level was
178 calculated using the following process: first, the linear spectral amplitude A_i was derived from the
179 logarithmic spectral amplitude a_i

180 using the equation $A_i = 10^{(a_i/10)}$. Subsequently, these linear amplitude values were converted to
181 PSD levels through the equation: $\text{PSD level (dB)} = 10 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sqrt{A_i}}{\text{BW}} \right)^2$, where BW is the bandwidth
182 (spectral resolution). Spectrograms were generated using a 16386-point Fast Fourier Transform
183 (FFT) with a Hanning window.

184 To compare the spectral profiles of natural soundscapes with the audiogram and sound
185 spectra of a soniferous fish species observed in the studied locations, we analysed a sound
186 recording of the croaking gourami *Trichopsis vittata* (obtained at 25°C) provided by F. Ladich and
187 used previously published auditory thresholds for this species (Wysocki et al., 2001). This allowed
188 us to compare auditory sensitivities between two sympatric species from the same family
189 (Osphronemidae) with contrasting behavioural-sensorial adaptations.

190

191 **Auditory Evoked Potential Measurements**

192 The Auditory Evoked Potential (AEP) recording protocol was according to prior studies
193 (Breitzler et al., 2020; Wong et al., 2022). Audiometry tests were conducted in a rectangular plastic
194 tank measuring 50 cm length x 35 cm width, and 23 cm height. An underwater speaker (UW30,
195 Electro-Voice, MN, USA) was placed at the bottom of the tank and surrounded by a layer of fine
196 sand. A custom-designed acoustic stimulation system was used for low frequencies (100 Hz),
197 featuring a vibrating plexiglass disc operated by a mini shaker (Brüel & Kjær 4810). This setup
198 was mounted at the center of the front-facing tank wall. The entire experimental arrangement was
199 placed on an anti-vibration air table (Vibraplane, KS Kinetic Systems, MA, USA) within a walk-
200 in soundproof chamber (120a-3, IAC Acoustics, North Aurora, IL, USA).

201 Adult *B. splendens* were initially subjected to a light anesthesia bath using 400 mg/L
202 tricaine methanesulfonate (MS-222, Arcos Organics, NJ, USA), buffered with double

203 concentration of sodium bicarbonate, until opercular movement ceased, which took approximately
204 3-5 min. The fish were placed in a specially designed sponge holder that immobilized them, with
205 a net partially covering the upper body, ensuring the fish's head remained just below the water
206 surface to allow normal breathing. Two stainless steel electrodes (0.40 mm diameter, 13 mm
207 length, Rochester Electro-Medical, Inc., FL, USA) were utilized, with the recording electrode
208 securely positioned against the skin over the brainstem area and the reference electrode placed on
209 the side of the body (Fig. 2).

210 Sound stimuli and AEP recordings were controlled via a TDT audiometry workstation
211 (Tucker-Davis Technologies, FL, USA). The AEP signal was transmitted into a low-impedance
212 head stage (RA4LI, TDT) that was connected to a pre-amplifier (RA4PA, TDT), and then band-
213 pass filtered (0.1–1 kHz) and digitized (16 bit, ± 4 mV). The output was finally sent to a Multi-I/O
214 processor (RZ6, TDT). While SigGen software allowed to generate sound stimuli, BioSig TDT
215 software controlled both signal presentation and acquisition. Stimuli consisted of 20 ms tone bursts
216 of 100, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 2000, 4000 and 6000 Hz, including 2 ms rise/fall ramps. Tone
217 stimuli were presented randomly at least 1000 times, half at opposite polarities (180° phase
218 shifted). The system was calibrated before each audiometry session by placing a hydrophone
219 (Brüel & Kjær 8104) connected to a sound level meter (Brüel & Kjær 2270) to verify the SPL at
220 the position occupied by the test subjects.

221 For each frequency, tones were initially presented at 140 dB re 1 μ Pa and then following 2.5 dB
222 decrements. The auditory threshold referred to the minimum required to elicit an identifiable and
223 reproducible AEP response in at least two averaged waveforms. To confirm an auditory response,
224 at least two of the following criteria were reached: (a) matching waveform shape compared to
225 previous sound level; (b) increased latency in a consistent AEP peak with decreasing sound level;

226 and/or (c) spectral peak in the FFT analysis of the AEP response that is twice the stimulation
227 frequency (Fig. 2).

228

229 **Statistical analysis**

230 The overall noise levels (L_{Zeq}) from the recording sites were compared using one-way
231 ANOVA, followed by post hoc Tukey tests to verify habitat specific differences.

232 Auditory thresholds at different frequencies from males and females were compared with
233 two-way repeated measures GLM with contrast analysis, with sex as a between-subject factor and
234 the different sound frequencies as repeated measures (within-subject factor). Parametric
235 assumptions were complied, namely data were normally distributed and variances were
236 homogeneous. The statistical analysis was performed with IBM SPSS v26 (IBM Corp. Armonk,
237 USA).

238

239 **Results**

240 **Characterization of natural habitat**

241 The Siamese fighting fish *B. splendens* were identified in different marshland habitats with
242 dense herbaceous vegetation, from lentic waterbodies in the mudflat to small canals near a lake.
243 All freshwater habitats exhibited common traits of low dissolved oxygen, from 0.19-0.37 mg/L
244 (CS1) in a small lentic canal to 2.87-3.02 mg/L in a small pool (CS2), with variable turbidity – see
245 Table 1, Fig. 1. Most of the habitats were very shallow, below 1 m (0.2-0.76 m), and only one
246 location (RST2) was slightly deeper (1.2 m). The overall water temperature varied between 22.1
247 and 25.1°C and presented low conductivity levels (<92.8 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$).

248 All five study sites consisted of quiet locations with similar noise levels (SPL or L_{Zeq}) and
249 low variability within each site ($CV < 3\%$). Overall, SPL varied between 101.6 ± 0.1 and $105.4 \pm$
250 2.9 dB re $1 \mu\text{Pa}$ (mean \pm standard deviation) (Table 2, Fig. 3). Nevertheless, significant differences
251 in SPL were found between recording sites ($F(4, 29) = 8.225$; $p < 0.001$), with RST2 showing
252 higher levels compared to the other sites (post hoc tests, $p \leq 0.003$) probably due to the constant
253 presence of insect sounds (Fig. 3B and Fig. 4).

254 Soundscapes from RST locations revealed distinct biological sounds, including potential
255 fish vocalizations: series of pulsed sounds < 2000 Hz (RST2) and short call with main energy
256 below 1000 Hz (RST3); birds singing at distance with main energy between 1000 - 7000 Hz
257 (RST2), but primarily insect sounds >2000 Hz, especially in RST2 (Fig. 3).

258 Soundscapes from RST locations revealed distinct biological sounds, including potential
259 fish vocalizations: series of pulsed sounds < 2000 Hz (RST2) and short call with main energy
260 below 1000 Hz (RST3); birds singing at distance with main energy between 1000 - 7000 Hz
261 (RST2), but primarily insect sounds >2000 Hz, especially in RST2 (Fig. 3). The soundscapes of
262 both CS1 and CS2 did not reveal obvious underwater biological activity, only a few instances of
263 abiotic sounds consisting of moving sediment and cavitation, and birds singing at distance.

264 The spectral profiles were similar across natural habitats, with most sound energy
265 concentrated below 1000 Hz and a gradual decline towards higher frequencies (Fig. 3).
266 Specifically, CS1 showed a distinct spectral peak around 500 - 1000 Hz, while CS2 exhibited a less
267 pronounced energy peak around 150 Hz, consisting of occasional moving sediment and cavitation
268 sounds, respectively (Fig. 3).

269

270 **Auditory sensitivity**

271 The Siamese fighting fish exhibited an overall auditory sensitivity bandwidth of 100-6000
272 Hz. The auditory thresholds were consistently the lowest at 100 Hz ($84.5 \text{ dB} \pm 5.2 \text{ dB}$, mean \pm
273 standard deviation; 75-95 dB range) and the highest at 4000 Hz ($137.8 \pm 3.6 \text{ dB}$; 130-140 range).
274 Since auditory responses at 4000 and 6000 Hz were not consistently present in all recordings, they
275 were excluded from statistical analysis. Auditory thresholds varied significantly with the
276 frequency tested ($F(6,54)=56.694$, $p < 0.001$), and sex-specific differences were also identified
277 ($F(1,9) = 10.123$, $p = 0.011$), with males showing lower thresholds at 400 Hz ($p = 0.015$) and 600
278 Hz ($p = 0.009$) compared to females. Such sex-specific differences between males and females
279 consisted of $11.9 \text{ dB} \pm 3.7$ at 400 Hz and $12.5 \text{ dB} \pm 3.8$ at 600 Hz (Fig. 5).

280 Furthermore, the species' auditory thresholds were above the spectral profiles of all natural
281 soundscapes at least 15 dB, indicating minimal possibility for auditory masking due to overall
282 background noise (Fig. 6).

283 We further compared these findings with the audiogram and sound spectra from
284 vocalizations emitted by *T. vittata* (Fig. 6). This soniferous fish exhibited lower auditory thresholds
285 at frequencies matching the primary spectral energy of its vocalizations within 800-2000 Hz. This
286 contrasted with *B. splendens*, which demonstrated highest sensitivity at lower frequencies below
287 400 Hz.

288

289

290

291 Discussion

292 The present work provides the first characterization of the underwater soundscape in the
293 natural habitats of the Siamese fighting fish *B. splendens*, specifically in quiet, lentic freshwater

294 systems within marshlands in Chiang Rai, Northern Thailand. In addition, we present the first
295 description of the auditory thresholds of *B. splendens*, showing sex-specific differences and higher
296 sensitivity to low frequencies compared to a sympatric vocal species. Overall, this study
297 establishes an important foundation for future research on the sensory adaptation of this air-
298 breathing anabantoid species, which is renowned for its significance in the ornamental fish market
299 and increasingly valued for genetic and behavioural research.

300

301 **Soundscapes from freshwater habitats**

302 Despite the critical role of freshwater ecosystems in sustaining fish diversity, limited
303 information is available on essential ecological parameters such as soundscape levels and
304 composition (Tonolla et al., 2010; Desjonquères et al., 2015; Lara & Vasconcelos, 2019; Rountree
305 et al., 2020; Decker et al., 2020).

306 The existing studies on habitat characterization of *B. splendens* have primarily focused on
307 typical ecological features such as water quality (Nur et al., 2022). According to these studies, the
308 species inhabits water bodies with low oxygen levels and muddy substrates, which were also
309 identified in the marshland habitats investigated in the present study.

310 However, freshwater habitats can be considerably variable and rich in acoustic information
311 providing important cues for fish orientation and survival. Noise levels in these environments
312 depend on factors such as water flow strength and substrate composition. Lakes and backwaters
313 typically exhibit lower noise levels compared to the fast-flowing waters found in streams and
314 rivers, with noise levels that can differ by over 40 dB (Amoser & Ladich, 2005, 2010; Wysocki et
315 al., 2007; Lara & Vasconcelos, 2019). Our results revealed relatively quiet soundscapes with SPL
316 around 102-105 dB re 1 μ Pa and low variability. Lara & Vasconcelos (2019) reported similar

317 values of 103-107 dB re 1 μ Pa in shallow pools and low-flow water courses with various substrates
318 (bedrock, sand, silt; maximum 50 cm depth) in Southwest India. In Austria, Wysocki et al. (2007)
319 measured 99, 98, and 110 dB re 1 μ Pa, for backwaters, pond and stream with bedrock substrate,
320 respectively.

321 Regarding noise spectral profiles, freshwater ecosystems such as ponds, small streams and
322 rivers typically show higher spectral energy at the lowest frequencies followed by a gradual noise
323 decline towards higher frequencies (Amoser & Ladich, 2005, 2010; Wysocki et al., 2007; Lara &
324 Vasconcelos, 2019). We also found a similar pattern of energy decline with increasing frequency
325 in all study sites, with most spectral energy below 1000 Hz. Since all habitats investigated were
326 relatively quiet, there was no distinct silent window related to sound propagation in the shallow
327 environment, as found in previous studies (Lugli, 2010; Lara & Vasconcelos, 2019).

328 Our sound recordings captured diverse biological sounds, including potential fish
329 vocalizations, but primarily insect sounds. Such biophony has been described in prior studies of
330 different freshwater habitats, such as ponds and rivers (Anderson et al., 2008; Montie, et al., 2015;
331 Desjonquères et al., 2020). Interestingly, in several of the study sites, we observed individuals of
332 the croaking gourami *T. vittata*. Although we cannot confirm the sound source, the pulsed temporal
333 patterns in the sound recording (Fig. 3C) suggest they might consist of calls from *T. vittata*. Future
334 research should include long-term recordings and visual censuses to accurately identify soniferous
335 fish species in these marshland habitats. Additionally, occasional abiotic sounds were also
336 detected, such as cavitation and moving substrate, consistent with other studies focusing on either
337 lentic or fast-flow water courses (Tonolla et al., 2011; Lara & Vasconcelos, 2019).

338 An important aspect concerns the quiet nature of the marshland habitats investigated.
339 Shallow and lentic freshwater ecosystems are known to be relatively quiet compared to

340 watercourses with higher hydrodynamics. These shallow habitats are particularly vulnerable to
341 climate change, overexploitation, water pollution, habitat destruction, and invasion by exotic
342 species (Dudgeon et al., 2007), including in Thailand (Pomoim et al., 2022). Additional
343 environmental stressors such as noise pollution could pose significant threats to the adaptation of
344 fish species and ultimately impact their community structure and ecosystem health.

345

346 **Auditory sensory adaptation**

347 We present the first description of the auditory thresholds of *B. splendens*, which revealed
348 an overall sensitivity bandwidth of 100-6000 Hz. The auditory thresholds were consistently the
349 lowest at 100 Hz (85 dB mean, 75-95 dB range) and a gradual increment was observed towards
350 higher frequencies, with highest thresholds recorded at 4000 Hz (138 dB, 130-140 dB range). Our
351 findings are consistent with previously reported audiograms for other anabantoid fishes, which
352 also showed enhanced sound-detecting abilities up to 5 kHz, the highest frequency tested (Ladich
353 & Yan, 1998). However, the best hearing sensitivities seem to vary considerably across
354 anabantoids. Ladich & Yan (1998) measured AEP recordings from five vocal species (*Trichopsis*
355 *vittata*, *T. pumila*, *Colisa lalia*, *Macropodus opercularis* and *Trichogaster trichopterus*), and
356 identified a high-frequency sensitivity peak between 800 Hz and 1500 Hz for all species (Ladich
357 & Yan, 1998). This sensitivity peak matched the dominant frequencies of their vocalizations in *T.*
358 *vittata* (1000-2000 Hz) and *C. lalia* (800-1000 Hz), but not in the smallest species *T. pumila* that
359 revealed best hearing below 1500 Hz and most sound energy at 1500-2500 Hz. According to
360 Ladich & Yan (1998), in vocal anabantoids, the association between high-pitched sounds and
361 enhanced hearing may be attributed to the suprabranchial air-breathing chamber. Positioned near

362 the auditory and sonic organs (pectoral fin tendons), this chamber may amplify both auditory
363 sensitivity and sound production at its resonant frequency.

364 In our study, *B. splendens* demonstrated best auditory sensitivity in the 100-400 Hz range,
365 with thresholds around 85-87 dB, which were notably lower compared to those observed in other
366 anabantoids within this frequency range.. Unlike other tested species from this group, and
367 following assays conducted in our lab (unpublished data), *B. splendens* does not seem to produce
368 vocalizations and lacks sonic organs (Ladich, 2001). Thus, differences in hearing curves between
369 the sympatric *B. splendens* and *T. vittata* may relate to the absence of acoustic signalling in the
370 former, although further research is needed to verify this hypothesis.

371 Furthermore, we identified sex-specific differences in *B. splendens*, with males exhibiting
372 lower thresholds, approximately 12-13 dB lower at 400 and 600 Hz compared to females. This
373 finding represents the first evidence of such differences among anabantoids and suggests a possible
374 correlation with variations in the suprabranchial air-breathing chamber, although other hypothesis
375 can be considered. Males of this species are known for their pronounced aggression and higher
376 oxygen demands, showing significantly more air breathing compared to females (Castro et al.,
377 2006; Alton et al., 2013). Such gender differences may have influenced the development and
378 morphology of the suprabranchial chamber, potentially affecting auditory sensitivity (Yan, 1998;
379 Ladich & Popper, 2004). Moreover, several studies focusing on soniferous fish have shown that
380 variations in gonadal state, circulating sex-steroids, and steroid receptor expression in peripheral
381 and central auditory structures are associated with changes in auditory sensitivity and inner ear
382 hair cell count (reviewed in Maruska & Sisneros, 2015).

383 Future research should explore potential sex-specific distinctions in the air-breathing organ
384 and inner ear sensory epithelia, as well as the potential influence of steroids, which are known to
385 influence aggression levels in males, on auditory thresholds of the study species.

386

387 In conclusion, the present work shows that *B. splendens* hearing range is best at low
388 frequencies, progressively decaying towards higher frequencies. Surprisingly, consistent
389 differences in hearing sensitivity between males and females were detected, calling for further
390 studies on the possible function and causes of this variability. The difference in auditory sensitivity
391 to the closely related and sympatric vocal species *T. vittata*, supports the hypothesis that
392 conspecific vocal communication is a significant selective pressure acting on auditory systems.
393 Lastly, the study shows that natural habitats of *B. splendens* are relatively silent, calling for the
394 attention to document and preserve soundscapes in conservation programs of freshwater habitats.

395

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402

403 **Competing Interests**

404 The authors declare there are no competing interests.

405

406 **Supplemental Information**

407 Supplemental data (AEP values and examples of sound recordings) can be found online at
408 supplementary materials.

409

410 **References**

411 Adamek-Urbańska D, Błażewicz E, Sobień M, Kasprzak R, Kamaszewski M. 2021.

412 Histological study of suprabranchial chamber membranes in Anabantoidei and Clariidae fishes.

413 *Animals*, **11**:1158. doi: 10.3390/ani11041158.

414 Alton LA, Portugal S, White, CR. 2013. Balancing the competing requirements of air-

415 breathing and display behaviour during male-male interactions in Siamese fighting fish *Betta*

416 *splendens*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology – A Molecular and Integrative Physiology*,

417 **164**:363–367. doi:10.1016/j.cbpa.2012.11.012

418 Amoser S, Ladich F. 2005. Are hearing sensitivities of freshwater fish adapted to the

419 ambient noise in their habitats? *Journal of Experimental Biology* **208**:3533–3542.

420 doi:10.1242/jeb.01809

421 Amoser S, Ladich F. 2010. Year-round variability of ambient noise in temperate

422 freshwater habitats and its implications for fishes. *Aquatic Sciences* **72**:371–378. doi: doi:

423 10.1007/s00027-010-0136-9

424 Anderson KA, Rountree RA, Juanes F. 2008. Soniferous fishes in the Hudson river.

425 *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society* **137**:616–626. doi: 10.1577/T05-220.1.

426 Belmar O, Booker D, Álvarez-Cabria M, Peñas FJ, Barquín J. 2019. Modelling physical
427 characteristics of river habitats. *River Research and Applications* **35**:804–817. doi:
428 10.1002/rra.3456

429 Breitzler L, Lau IH, Fonseca PJ, Vasconcelos RO. 2020. Noise-induced hearing loss in
430 zebrafish: investigating structural and functional inner ear damage and recovery. *Hearing*
431 *Research* **391**:107952. doi:10.1016/j.heares.2020.107952

432 Castro N, Ros AFH, Becker K, Oliveira, RF. 2006. Metabolic costs of aggressive
433 behaviour in the Siamese fighting fish, *Betta splendens*. *Aggressive Behavior*, **32**:474-480.
434 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ab.20147>

435 Cerezer FO, Dambros CS, Coelho MTP, Cassemiro FAS, Barreto E, Albert JS, Wuest RO,
436 Graham CH. 2023. Accelerated body size evolution in upland environments is correlated with
437 recent speciation in South American freshwater fishes. *Nature Communications* **14**:6070. doi:
438 10.1038/s41467-023-41812-7.

439 Decker E, Parker B, Linke S, Capon S, Sheldon F. 2020. Singing streams: Describing
440 freshwater soundscapes with the help of acoustic indices. *Ecology and Evolution* **10**:4979-4989.
441 doi: 10.1002/ece3.6251.

442 Desjonquères C, Rybak F, Depraetere M, Gasc A, Le Viol I, Pavoine S, Sueur J. 2015.
443 First description of underwater acoustic diversity in three temperate ponds. *PeerJ* **3**. doi:
444 10.7717/peerj.1393.

445 Desjonquères C, Rybak F, Ulloa JS, Kempf A, Hen AB, Sueur J. 2020. Monitoring the
446 acoustic activity of an aquatic insect population in relation to temperature, vegetation, and noise.
447 *Freshwater Biology* **65**:107–116. doi:10.1111/fwb.13171.

448 Dudgeon D, Arthington AH, Gessner MO, Kawabata ZI, Knowler DJ, Lévêque C,
449 Naiman RJ, Prieur-Richard AH, Soto D, Stiassny MLJ. 2006. Freshwater biodiversity:
450 importance, threats, status and conservation challenges. *Biological Reviews* **81**:163-182. doi:
451 10.1017/S1464793105006950

452 Fan G, Chan J, Ma K, Yang B, Zhang H, Shi C, Lae H, Ren Z, Xu Q, Wang J, Chen W,
453 Shao L, Gonçalves D, Ramos A, Cardoso SD, Guo M, Cai J, Xu X, Wang J, Yang H, Liu X,
454 Wang Y. 2018. Chromosome-level reference genome of the siamese fighting fish *Betta*
455 *splendens*, a model species for the study of aggression. *Gigascience*. **7**. doi:
456 10.1093/gigascience/giy087

457 Fay R. 2009. Soundscapes and the sense of hearing of fishes. *Integrative Zoology* **4**:26–
458 32. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-4877.2008.00132.x

459 Hawkins AD, Popper AN. 2018. Directional hearing and sound source localization by
460 fishes. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **144**:3329–3350.
461 <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5082306>

462 Hui TH, Ng PK. 2005. The fighting fishes (Teleostei: Osphronemidae: genus *Betta*) of
463 Singapore, Malaysia and Brunei. *The Raffles Bulletin of Zoology* **13**:43-99.

464 Kowasupat C, Panijpan B, Ruenwongsa P. 2012. *Betta siamorientalis*, a new species of
465 bubble-nest building fighting fish (Teleostei: Osphronemidae) from eastern Thailand. *Vertebrate*
466 *Zoology* **62**:387-397. doi: 10.3897/vz.62.e31398

467 Kwon Y, Vranken N, Hoge C, Lichak M, Norovich A, Francis K, Camacho-Garcia J,
468 Bista I, Wood J, Mccarthy S, Chow W, Tan HH, Howe K, Bandara S, Lintig JV, Ruber L,
469 Durbin R, Svardal H, Bendesky A. 2022. Genomic consequences of domestication of the
470 Siamese fighting fish. *Science Advances* **8**. DOI:10.1126/sciadv.abm4950

471 Ladich F, Yan HY. 1998. Correlation between auditory sensitivity and vocalization in
472 anabantoid fishes. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, **182**:737-746. doi:
473 10.1007/s003590050218

474 Ladich F. 2000. Acoustic communication and the evolution of hearing in fishes.
475 *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **355**:1285-8. doi:
476 10.1098/rstb.2000.0685.

477 Ladich F, Popper AN. 2001. Comparison of the inner ear ultrastructure between teleost
478 fishes using different channels for communication. *Hearing Research*, **154**:62-72. doi:
479 10.1016/S0378-5955(01)00217-9.

480 Ladich F, Popper AN. 2004. Parallel evolution in fish hearing organs. In: Manley G, Fay
481 RR, Popper AN, editors. *Evolution of the Vertebrate Auditory System*. New York: Springer-
482 Verlag 95–127.

483 Ladich F. 2007. Females whisper briefly during sex: context- and sex-specific differences
484 in sounds made by croaking gouramis. *Animal Behaviour*, **73**: 379-387.

485 doi:10.1016/j.anbehav.2006.04.014.

486 Lara RA, Vasconcelos RO. 2019. Characterization of the natural soundscape of zebrafish
487 and comparison with the captive noise conditions. *Zebrafish* **16**:152-164. doi:

488 10.1089/zeb.2018.1654.

489 Lagardere JP, Begout ML, Lafaye JY, Villotte JP. 1994. Influence of wind-produced
490 noise on orientation in the Sole (*Solea solea*). *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic*

491 *Sciences* **51**:1258–1264. <https://doi.org/10.1139/f94-125>

492 Lugli, M. 2010. Sounds of shallow water fishes pitch within the quiet window of the
493 habitat ambient noise. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, **196**:439-451. doi:

494 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00359-010-0528-2>

495 Maruska KP, Sisneros, JA. 2015. Sex Steroid-Dependent Modulation of Acoustic
496 Communication Systems in Fishes. In: Ladich, F. (eds) Sound Communication in Fishes. Animal
497 Signals and Communication, vol 4. Springer, Vienna. [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-1846-](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-1846-7_7)

498 [7_7](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-1846-7_7)

499 Manel S, Guerin PE, Mouillot D, Blanchet S, Velez L, Albouy C, Pellissier L. 2020.
500 Global determinants of freshwater and marine fish genetic diversity. *Nature Communications*

501 **11**:692. doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-14409-7.

- 502 Montie EW, Vega S, Powell M. 2015. Seasonal and spatial patterns of fish sound
503 production in the May River, South Carolina. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society*
504 **144**:705–716. doi: 10.1080/00028487.2015.1037014.
- 505 Nakatani M, Miya M, Mabuchi K, Saitoh K, Nishida M. 2011. Evolutionary history of
506 Otophysi (Teleostei), a major clade of the modern freshwater fishes: Pangaeen origin and
507 Mesozoic radiation. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* **11**:177. doi: 10.1186/1471-2148-11-177.
- 508 Nur FM, Batubara AS, Fadli N, Rizal S, Siti-Azizah MN, Muchlisin ZA. 2022. Diversity,
509 distribution, and conservation status of *Betta* fish (Teleostei: Osphronemidae) in Aceh Waters,
510 Indonesia. *The European Zoological Journal* **89**:142-151.
511 <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750263.2022.2029587>
- 512 Palmiotti A, Lichak M, Shih P, Bendesky A. 2023. Genetic manipulation of *Betta* fish.
513 *Frontiers in Genome* **5**:1167093. doi: 10.1101/2023.02.16.528733.
- 514 Panijpan B, Sriwattananarothai N, Kowasupat C, Ruenwongsa P, Jeenthong T,
515 Phumchoosri A. 2017. Biodiversity of bubble-nest building and mouth-brooding fighting fish
516 species of the genus *Betta* in Southeast Asia. *The Thailand Natural History Museum Journal* **11**:
517 1–21.
- 518 Picado A, Mendes J, Ruela R, Pinheiro J, Dias JM. 2020. Physico-chemical
519 characterization of two Portuguese coastal systems: Ria de Alvor and Mira Estuary. *Journal of*
520 *Marine Science and Engineering* **8**:537. doi: 10.3390/jmse8070537.

- 521 Pomoim N, Hughes AC, Trisurat Y, Corlett RT. 2022. Vulnerability to climate change of
522 species in protected areas in Thailand. *Scientific Reports* **12**:5705. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-
523 09767-9
- 524 Popper AN, Hawkins AD. 2019. An overview of fish bioacoustics and the impacts of
525 anthropogenic sounds on fishes. *Journal of Fish Biology* **94**:692-713. doi: 10.1111/jfb.13948.
- 526 Popper AN, Hawkins, AD. 2021. Fish hearing and how it is best determined. *ICES*
527 *Journal of Marine Science*, **78**:2325-2336. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab115>
- 528 Putland RL, Montgomery JC, Radford CA. 2019. Ecology of fish hearing. *Journal of*
529 *Fish Biology* **95**:39-52. doi: 10.1111/jfb.13867.
- 530 Ramos A, Gonçalves D. 2019. Artificial selection for male winners in the Siamese
531 fighting fish, *Betta splendens*, correlates with high female aggression. *Frontiers in Zoology*
532 **16**:34. doi: 10.1186/s12983-019-0333-x.
- 533 Ramos A, Gonçalves D. 2022. Selection for winners impacts the endocrine system in the
534 Siamese fighting fish. *General and Comparative Endocrinology* **318**:113988. doi:
535 10.1016/j.ygcen.2022.113988
- 536 Rountree RA, Juanes F, Bolgan M. 2020. Temperate freshwater soundscapes: A
537 cacophony of undescribed biological sounds now threatened by anthropogenic noise. *Plos One*
538 **15**. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0221842.
- 539 Su H, Feng Y, Chen J, Chen J, Ma S, Fang J, Xie P. 2021. Determinants of trophic
540 cascade strength in freshwater ecosystems: a global analysis. *Ecology* **102**. doi:
541 10.1002/ecy.3370.

542 Thomson JR, Taylor MP, Fryirs KA, Brierley GJ. 2001. A geomorphological framework
543 for river characterization and habitat assessment. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater*
544 *Ecosystems* **11**:373-389. doi: 10.1002/aqc.467.

545 Tonolla D, Acuña V, Lorang MS, Heutschi K, Tockner K. 2010. A field-based
546 investigation to examine underwater soundscapes of five common river habitats. *Hydrological*
547 *Processes* **24**:3146–3156. doi: 10.1002/hyp.7730.

548 Tonolla D, Lorang MS, Heutschi K, Gotschalk CC, Tockner K. 2011. Characterization of
549 spatial heterogeneity in underwater soundscapes at the river segment scale. *Limnology and*
550 *Oceanography* **56**:2319–2333. doi:10.4319/lo.2011.56.6.2319.

551 Tudor M, Lopez-Anido RN, Yocius CA, Conlin SM, Hamlin HJ. 2019. Ecologically
552 relevant arsenic exposure alters female mate preference and anxiety-like behavior in betta
553 splendens. *Heliyon*, **5**. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02646>

554 Veith J, Chaigne T, Svanidze A, Dressler LE, Hoffman M, Gerhardt B, Judkewitz B.
555 2024. The mechanism for directional hearing in fish. *Nature*. **631**:118-124. doi:
556 10.1038/s41586-024-07507

557 Villéger S, Brosse S, Mouchet M, Mouillot D, Vanni MJ. 2017. Functional ecology of
558 fish: current approaches and future challenges. *Aquatic Science* **79**:783-801. doi:
559 10.1007/s00027-017-0546-z.

560 Yan HY. 1998. Auditory role of the suprabranchial chamber in gourami fish. *Journal of*
561 *Comparative Physiology A*. **183**:325-33. doi: 10.1007/s003590050259.

562 Wysocki LE, Ladich F. 2001. The ontogenetic development of auditory sensitivity,
563 vocalization and acoustic communication in the labyrinth fish *Trichopsis vittata*. *Journal of*
564 *Comparative Physiology A*, **187**:177-187. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003590100186>

565 Wysocki LE, Amoser S, Ladich F. 2007. Diversity in ambient noise in European
566 freshwater habitats: noise levels, spectral profiles, and impact on fishes. *Journal of the*
567 *Acoustical Society of America* **121**: 2559–2566. doi: 10.1121/1.2713661

568 Wong MI, Lau IH, Gordillo-Martinez F, Vasconcelos RO. 2022. The effect of time
569 regime in noise exposure on the auditory system and behavioural stress in the zebrafish.
570 *Scientific Reports* **12**:15353. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-19573-y

571

572 **Captions**

573 Fig. 1. Geographical locations of the different study sites in Northern Thailand, Chiang Rai
574 Province, where wild Siamese fighting fish (*Betta splendens*) were identified and sound
575 recordings conducted. (Top row) Grey map highlights the two major locations: Chiang Saen
576 District (CS) and the Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST), Wiang Chai District. Satellite images
577 (Google Earth) of the respective locations are shown to provide topographical details. (Bottom
578 row) Images from each sampling site during recordings: CS1 – drainage canal bordered by tall,
579 dense vegetation; CS2 – water body within an extensive mudflat with short herbaceous
580 vegetation; RST1 – canal surrounded by dense vegetation with the presence of water buffalos;
581 RST2 and RST3 – water bodies in marshland with diverse herbaceous plants. Each image shows
582 the hydrophone attached to a rod fixed to the bottom (see white arrow for an example). An image

583 captured by an underwater camera in one of the study sites shows water visibility (top right) and
584 a bubble nest (bottom right) are also presented.

585

586 Fig. 2. Examples of Auditory Evoked Potential (AEP) response curves of *B. splendens* males in
587 response to A) 400 Hz and B) 800 Hz tone stimuli presented at decreasing amplitudes (dB values
588 are indicated for each AEP curve). Auditory thresholds (indicated by asterisks) were identified as
589 the lowest amplitude at which a consistent response curve pattern could be observed. Voltage
590 scales were adjusted to enhance visibility and correspond to the AEP curves presented below. C)
591 Test specimen positioned on a sponge holder in the AEP recordings setup.

592

593 Fig. 3. A) Power Spectral Density (PSD) of ambient noise from diverse marshland habitats
594 recorded in Chiang Saen District (CS) and Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST). Sampling frequency:
595 48 kHz, FFT size 16384. (B) Spectrogram from RST2 presenting high-pitched insect calls
596 (between 10-15 kHz) and potential fish sounds - marked (white square) and detailed in C); D)
597 and E) oscillogram and spectrogram of cavitation sounds (from RST2) and possible fish sound
598 (from CS1), respectively. FFT size 2048.

599

600 Fig. 4. Comparison of mean Sound Pressure Level (\pm standard deviation) between different
601 recording sites in Chiang Saen District (CS) and Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST) ($F(4, 29) =$
602 8.225 ; $p < 0.001$). Each averaged value was based on six measurements (linear equivalent, LZeq)
603 per site over 60 s period. Distinct letters indicate statistically significant differences as
604 determined by pairwise post hoc comparisons.

605

606 Fig. 5. Mean auditory thresholds (\pm standard error of the mean or SEM) of males (dashed line)
607 and females (continuous line) *B. splendens* ($F(1,9) = 10.123$, $p = 0.011$). Asterisks indicate sex-
608 specific differences at 400 Hz ($p = 0.015$) and 600 Hz ($p = 0.009$). Data presented is based on 8
609 months old fish, consisting of similar sized individuals – 5 males and 6 females. A wild type
610 specimen, originating from adult fish from Chiang Rai, Thailand (top).

611

612 Fig. 6. Sound spectra from the natural habitats of *B. splendens* (sampling frequency 48 kHz, FFT
613 size 2048) and mean auditory thresholds from the study species and a sympatric vocal fish
614 croaking gourami *Trichopsis vittata* (source: Wysocki & Ladich, 2001). Grey line represents the
615 croaking sound from *T. vittata* recorded at 25°C (provided by F. Ladich, sampling frequency
616 44.1 kHz, bypass filtered between 0.2-3.5 kHz, FFT size 2048). Drawing of *T. vittata* based on
617 Ladich (2007).

618

Figure 1

Geographical locations of the different study sites in Northern Thailand.

Geographical locations of the different study sites in Northern Thailand, Chiang Rai Province, where wild Siamese fighting fish (*Betta splendens*) were identified and sound recordings conducted. (Top row) Grey map highlights the two major locations: Chiang Saen District (CS) and the Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST), Wiang Chai District. Satellite images (Google Earth) of the respective locations are shown to provide topographical details. (Bottom row) Images from each sampling site during recordings: CS1 - drainage canal bordered by tall, dense vegetation; CS2 - water body within an extensive mudflat with short herbaceous vegetation; RST1 - canal surrounded by dense vegetation with the presence of water buffalos; RST2 and RST3 - water bodies in marshland with diverse herbaceous plants. Each image shows the hydrophone attached to a rod fixed to the bottom (see white arrow for an example). An image captured by an underwater camera in one of the study sites shows water visibility (top right) and a bubble nest (bottom right) are also presented.

Figure 2

Auditory Evoked Potential responses of *B. splendens*.

Examples of Auditory Evoked Potential (AEP) response curves of *B. splendens* males in response to A) 400 Hz and B) 800 Hz tone stimuli presented at decreasing amplitudes (dB values are indicated for each AEP curve). Auditory thresholds (indicated by asterisks) were identified as the lowest amplitude at which a consistent response curve pattern could be observed. Voltage scales were adjusted to enhance visibility and correspond to the AEP curves presented below. C) Test specimen positioned on a sponge holder in the AEP recordings setup.

Figure 3

Power Spectral Density (PSD) of ambient noise from diverse marshland habitats and sound examples from different abiotic and biotic sources.

A) Power Spectral Density (PSD) of ambient noise from diverse marshland habitats recorded in Chiang Saen District (CS) and Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST). Sampling frequency: 48 kHz, FFT size 16384. (B) Spectrogram from RST2 presenting high-pitched insect calls (between 10-15 kHz) and potential fish sounds - marked (white square) and detailed in C); D) and E) oscillogram and spectrogram of cavitation sounds (from RST2) and possible fish sound (from CS1), respectively. FFT size 2048.

Figure 4

Comparison of Sound Pressure Level between different recording sites.

Comparison of mean Sound Pressure Level (\pm standard deviation) between different recording sites in Chiang Saen District (CS) and Rai Son Thon Reservoir (RST) ($F(4, 29) = 8.225$; $p < 0.001$). Each averaged value was based on six measurements (linear equivalent, LZeq) per site over 60 s period. Distinct letters indicate statistically significant differences as determined by pairwise post hoc comparisons.

Figure 5

Mean auditory thresholds of *B. splendens*.

Mean auditory thresholds (\pm standard error of the mean or SEM) of males (dashed line) and females (continuous line) *B. splendens* ($F(1,9) = 10.123$, $p = 0.011$). Asterisks indicate sex-specific differences at 400 Hz ($p = 0.015$) and 600 Hz ($p = 0.009$). Data presented is based on 8 months old fish, consisting of similar sized individuals - 5 males and 6 females. A wild type specimen, originating from adult fish from Chiang Rai, Thailand (top).

Figure 6

Sound spectra from the natural habitats of *B. splendens* and auditory thresholds from the study species and a sympatric vocal fish croaking gourami.

Sound spectra from the natural habitats of *B. splendens* (sampling frequency 48 kHz, FFT size 2048) and mean auditory thresholds from the study species and a sympatric vocal fish croaking gourami *Trichopsis vittata* (source: Wysocki & Ladich, 2001). Grey line represents the croaking sound from *T. vittata* recorded at 25°C (provided by F. Ladich, sampling frequency 44.1 kHz, bypass filtered between 0.2-3.5 kHz, FFT size 2048). Drawing of *T. vittata* based on Ladich (2007).

1 Table 1- Characterization of the study sites within the marshland habitats of *B. splendens* at Chiang Saen Lake, Chiang Saen District
 2 (CS1 and CS2) and the Rai Son Thon Reservoir, Wiang Chai District (RST1, RST2 and RST3).

Location	GPS coordinates	Habitat	Elevation (m)	Water temp. (°C)	Depth (m)	Salinity (ppt)	Conductivity (µs/cm)	pH	DO (mg/L)
CS1	20°15'51.14"N 0° 2'46.67"E	Drainage canal bordered by tall vegetation	371	22.5	0.30	0.04	81.3-81.5	5.6-5.7	0.19-0.37
CS2	20°15'58.46"N 100° 2'33.03"E	Water body within extensive mudflat with short herbaceous plants	369	24.4-25.1	0.16	0.01	33.2-33.5	5.4-5.5	2.87-3.02
RST1	19°49'27.56"N 99°59'10.39"E	Canal with dense vegetation and presence of water buffalos	391	24.4	0.20	0.04	92.8	5.8	0.40
RST2	19°50'5.19"N 100° 0'12.77"E	Water body within mudflat surrounded by herbaceous plants	393	22.1	1.20	0.03	53.5-54.2	4.8-4.9	0.38-0.64
RST3	19°50'6.55"N 100° 0'11.22"E	Water body within mudflat surrounded by herbaceous plants	393	22.6	0.76	0.02	47.1-59.8	5.6-5.6	0.61-0.64

3

4

5

1 Table 2 – Mean Sound Pressure Levels (dB re 1 μ Pa) \pm Standard Deviation (SD) measured at five study sites at Chiang Saen Lake,
2 Chiang Saen District (CS1 and CS2) and the Rai Son Thon Reservoir, Wiang Chai District (RST1, RST2 and RST3). (Mean values
3 were determined from six readings based on 60 s; CV, coefficient of variation)

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Location	Mean \pm SD	Min	Max	CV (%)
CS1	102.2 \pm 0.5	102.2	105.5	0.53
CS2	102.2 \pm 0.3	102.1	104.0	0.32
RST1	101.6 \pm 0.1	101.8	104.7	0.12
RST2	105.4 \pm 2.9	104.5	108.6	2.78
RST3	101.8 \pm 0.2	101.9	104.2	0.16